

PANDEMIC PERIOD PREGNANT IN WOMEN CHANGES

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Annotation. So far, the evidence suggests that the risk of miscarriage is not high in pregnant women with COVID-19. To date, some cases of intrauterine or perinatal infection have been reported in existing scientific studies, but this is very rare and COVID-19 infection is unlikely to cause fetal malformation. The few cases known in infants with coronavirus infection in the early days are mild. There are no serious cases in our observations. In terms of maternal complications, the most complex pneumonias occur during this period in the third trimester of pregnancy or in the postpartum period, i.e., a few weeks after birth, in unvaccinated pregnant women. COVID-19 infection in the first and second trimesters of pregnancy is associated with a number of complications. However, due to complications in the mother (especially in the third trimester of pregnancy), the frequency of preterm births has increased.

Key word: Pandemic , Pregnancy, Abortion.

Relevance. The disease appears to be exacerbated during pregnancy and in pregnant women. As a result, preterm birth in pregnant women and an increase in maternal acute pneumonia have led to an increase in fetal miscarriage in pregnant women as a result of respiratory dysfunction and impaired fetal oxygen supply. This situation increased the risk to the mother's life. Prevention of coronavirus infection is the most important task for pregnant women. Pregnant women may experience changes in their immune system, which makes them more susceptible to respiratory viruses. These changes mean that expectant mothers should be proactive about safety measures. However, we know that high fever during pregnancy, especially in the first trimester, can increase the risk of birth defects. We therefore urge our patients to be protected from all diseases that cause fever, including influenza. COVID 19 may increase the risk of premature or premature birth. If you experience the following symptoms during pregnancy, you should contact an obstetrician immediately:

- Changes in the baby's movements
- Vaginal bleeding
- Persistent clear vaginal discharge
- Abdominal pain
- Shrinkage before 37 weeks
- Fever
- Headache
- Sudden swelling of your hands or face

The new corona virus can pose a risk to the pregnant woman herself. Publications on cases of coronary infections during pregnancy indicate that the complications associated with the disease are higher in pregnant women than in non-pregnant women of the same age. It is difficult to say exactly how the virus affects the female body. In general, there are no clear differences in how other patients become ill. However, there may be some difficulties and complications. If a woman suffers from chronic diseases such as kidney or liver disease, diabetes or asthma, she is at risk. Even if a woman is seriously ill, problems can arise. The growing fetus puts pressure on the heart and lungs, blocking blood and circulation.

The purpose of our study. To reduce the process of natural abortion in pregnant women with COVID-19 and to form a prophylactic process to prevent birth defects in the child in the postpartum process. A comparative comparison of preterm births during a pandemic.

Materials and methods. Our goal was to compare the incidence of premature miscarriage, premature birth in pregnant women with COVID-19 during 2020-2021. In pregnant women with

COVID-19, these processes were also assessed based on the functional status of the pregnant woman, and we analyzed the following cases with high levels of COVID-19. The following conditions or factors can lead to serious illness from COVID-19 during pregnancy: • Over 35 years of age • Overweight or obesity • High blood pressure (before pregnancy) • Diabetes mellitus - Type 1 or 2 (before pregnancy) can be found. the risk of serious illness from your COVID-19.

Inspection results and conclusions.

In our follow-up, the main symptoms in pregnant women were as follows. Symptoms of coronavirus infection in pregnant women did not differ from the symptoms commonly found in other infected people: • fever - in 90% of cases; • dry or mild sputum cough - in about 80% of clinical cases; • shortness of breath; • chest compression; • high level of fatigue, decreased performance; • diarrhea, nausea, vomiting; • Headache.

However, the symptom complex may vary individually for each pregnant woman. Sometimes a woman feels a slight discomfort that can be confused with the appearance of a normal cold. A comparison of 55 pregnant women with COVID-19 in 2020 and 59 16-week-old pregnant women in 2021 was developed at the treatment facility for patients with coronavirus infection in Surkhandarya region. The incidence of miscarriages in pregnant women with pregnancies less than 16 weeks was 20% in 2020 and 23.73% in 2021. The number of pregnant women at 16-28 weeks was 110 in 2020 and 132 in 2021. Premature births in pregnant women in 2020 were 22.8 percent. In 2021, this figure rose to 26.51% again. The number of pregnant women at 28-37 weeks was 90 in 2020 and 293 in 2021. During this period, 24.44% of pregnant women gave birth prematurely in 2020 and 15.36% in 2021. Date of operation Termez Central Hospital 2021 07.07.2021. As of March 26, 2021, 537 pregnant women were hospitalized, 160 of whom gave birth at the same time. In July and August 2021, 116 caesarean sections were performed on pregnant women with COVID-19. The test for COVID-19 was negative in all newborns.

Conclusion.

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